

Gaussians as Both Solutions of the Schrodinger Equation and Maximum Entropy Calculations

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Recently, maximum entropy calculations have become associated with solutions of the single particle Schrodinger equation. In some cases, the single particle Schrodinger equation has been altered to represent a single quantum particle with a temperature-Shannon entropy term added. In other cases, Tsallis entropy has been maximized subject to constraints to obtain the ground state single particle wavefunction for T (temperature)=0. In both cases, Gaussian wavefunctions have played a key role. The purpose of this note, is to examine the link between the Schrodinger equation and maximum entropy for the case of Gaussian wavefunctions (and hence densities). In particular, we show that a Shannon entropy term is included in the single particle Schrodinger equation for a Gaussian wavefunction and an r^2 type of potential. The quantum density in such a case also maximizes Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on the integral of r^2 times density. We also point out that the solution of the time independent Schrodinger equation represents a resonance $\exp(iEt)$ where E is the energy which does not seem to appear in statistical mechanics. If there is a link between the Schrodinger equation and maximization of entropy, perhaps classical statistical systems can also exhibit a time resonance.

$T > 0$ Single Particle Schrodinger Equation

In [14], Shannon's entropy $-\int d \ln(d)$ (where d is the density) is maximized subject to the constraints $(\int d = 1)$ and $(\int H d = \text{Energy})$ where H is the Hamiltonian. The main equation developed in [14] is:

$$H W + T W \ln(W^* W / d_1) = g W \quad (1)$$

Here H is the Hamiltonian, W the wavefunction, g a constant and d_1 an "a priori" density which is often taken as 1 in the calculations. In other words, one has a Schrodinger type equation, with a type of Shannon's entropy term with a W^* removed.

Equation (1) is solved in [14] for a number of cases, and although not all involve Gaussian wavefunctions, two do, namely the solution for a free particle and that for a harmonic oscillator. More will be said on this later in a section linking Shannon's entropy to the Schrodinger equation for the case of a Gaussian wavefunction.

Maximizing Tsallis Entropy to Obtain Ground State Single Particle Wavefunctions at Zero Temperature

In [12] and other papers, the goal of the authors is to obtain the ground state wavefunction of the single particle without solving the Schrodinger equation, but rather using constraints and the maximization of Tsallis entropy (which is a generalized entropy form). For the case of q-Gaussians (for example $W(r)=C[1-(q-1)b r^2]^{-1/(q-1)}$) in r space and also in momentum space, they are able to find solutions which maximize Tsallis entropy and are also solutions of the Schrodinger equation for certain potentials. These potentials turn out to be the harmonic oscillator and 1/r Coulomb potentials in certain limits and so are of importance. It should be noted that as q approaches 1 W(r) approaches a Gaussian. In fact, the q-Gaussian form is the regular "limit" form for an exponential. (It should be noted that Kaniadakis has also used a similar form for his relativistic distribution although it is not quadratic in r or p, but rather linear in energy.) Thus, in [12], Gaussians (and limiting functions which become Gaussians) maximize an entropy type of equation as well as solve the Schrodinger equation. It should be noted that in [12] the expectation of r^2 is used as the constraint in maximizing Tsallis entropy. If one used the same constraint (integral density r^2) maximizing Shannon's entropy, one would immediately obtain a Gaussian solution.

Gaussian Wavefunctions

Let us consider the Schrodinger equation:

$$W^* \hbar^2 \text{grad}^2 / 2m W + V(r) W = E W$$

Upon obtaining a solution for W, the wavefunction, one may argue that $\int W^* V(r) W = \text{constant}$ is a constraint. Applying this to the maximization of Shannon's entropy yields

$$\int d \ln(d) - b \int d V(r) \quad \text{where } d=\text{density}=W^* W \text{ and } b \text{ is a Lagrange multiplier}$$

Maximizing with respect to d (density) yields d proportional to $\exp [-bV(r)]$. Such a factor is common in statistical mechanics, but does not represent $W^*(r)W(r)$, the quantum mechanical density in general. Let us, however, consider the case of a Gaussian wavefunction i.e.. $W(r) = \exp [- V(r)/2]$ where V(r) is proportional to r^2 . Then:

$V(r) W = - W \ln(W^*W)$ in the Schrodinger equation and there is a link between the time independent Schrodinger equation (for the Gaussian wavefunction) and Shannon's entropy. In fact, this term already mimics the extra term added in [14] to describe a single particle with a maximum entropy term and an associated temperature. In such a case, the Gaussian is both a solution of the Schrodinger equation and the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint: integral r^2 density.

Thus it is no surprise that in [14], Gaussian wavefunctions were found for the generalized equation (1) for a free particle and a harmonic oscillator. The additional term in the otherwise conventional Schrodinger equation (of (1)) is equivalent (up to the factor of T) to $V(r)W(r)$ for V(r)

proportional to r^2 . In the case of the harmonic potential, the additional term is again equivalent to the r^2 term.

It should be pointed out, however, that in the case of the Schrodinger equation, H is part of an evolution operator [$\exp(iHt)$] and that the Schrodinger eigenvalue equation represents a time evolution of $\exp(iEt)$ or a resonance in time. For people who take zitterbewegung seriously, this resonance may be related to a physical resonance occurring in the quantum system. For example, in the 2x2 matrix problem [2]-[9], the resonance is related to backward and forward motion as a particle moves forward with an average speed of v . Thus, there seems to be extra physics described by the wavefunction and the density W^*W washes out some of these details.

In [10], it was suggested that the Schrodinger equation be used to describe a classical gas in a rotating cylinder. This is again a Gaussian problem with the statistical mechanical spatial density given by $\exp(-.5 \omega^2 r^2/T)$ where ω is the angular frequency. One may argue that this is a coincidence as it has been shown that Gaussian wavefunction solutions of the Schrodinger equation can also be solutions of maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to an integral r^2 density constraint. An interesting question, however, arises as to whether the Schrodinger equation approach to this classical problem indicates that there is a resonance in the system (perhaps associated with sound waves). Solutions of the time independent Schrodinger equation are resonances, but are also statistical. In statistical mechanics, one does not have this resonance, as only density is used which would not show the resonance. For quantum mechanics, $W^* \exp(-iEt) W \exp(iEt)$ also exhibits no resonance because the time portions cancel.

There is further importance related to a Gaussian density due to the Central Limit Theorem. Some people argue that a Gaussian density implies randomness because of the Central Limit Theorem, but the quantum mechanical problem (which has a Gaussian wavefunction W proportional to $\exp(-x^2/2)$) represents a time resonance (i.e. periodicity) which implies some kind of order even though the spatial density W^*W is a Gaussian.

One may also argue that a Gaussian wavefunction is only one of many possible wavefunctions and so the link with statistical mechanics is a mathematical coincidence. In [12], however, q-Gaussians which become Gaussians under a certain limit, are part of the solution of the harmonic oscillator Schrodinger equation and the $1/r$ Coulomb problem. Thus, these are very common quantum mechanical problems and any link to statistical mechanics for the temperature=0 single particle time-independent Schrodinger equation is important, especially because it might link the two statistical approaches, namely that of quantum mechanics and statistical mechanics.

Conclusion

There is some work in the literature [12], [14], which attempts to link entropy with the Schrodinger equation, although in different ways. In [14], the Schrodinger equation itself is modified by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to $\langle W H W \rangle = E$ and $\langle W W \rangle = 1$ where W is the wavefunction. A new equation (1) which is a combination of the time independent

Schrodinger equation with an extra Shannon entropy term with a coefficient of T (temperature) is obtained. In two cases, that for a free particle and that for a harmonic oscillator, Gaussian solutions are obtained.

In this note, we show that for a $V(r)$ proportional to r^2 , $V(r)W(r)$ where V is the potential and W the wavefunction, is equivalent to a Shannon type entropy term $W(r) \ln(W^* W)$ where W is a Gaussian type $\exp(-.5ar^2)$ and density also a Gaussian $\exp(-ar^2)$. Thus, maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint integral density $V(r)$ or solving the Schrodinger equation give Gaussian solutions and it appears that there is link between the maximization of entropy of statistical mechanics the solution of the Schrodinger equation for the Gaussian case (or even q-Gaussian forms). This of course begs the question of what is happening with other types of wavefunctions. One thing that is interesting is that the solution of the Schrodinger equation, which is probabilistic, is also associated with a time resonance $\exp(iHt)$ which may be related to physical periodical motion (zitterbewegung for example in a system). It seems that if the Schrodinger equation and the maximization of entropy are linked, at least in some cases, there might also be a periodic phenomenon in classical statistical systems. [10]

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